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OVERVIEW MUCOADHESIVE MICROSPHERE: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Now a day those dosage form which can control the release rate. The microspheres are producing target drug delivery at specific time limit. Microspheres are making important part in novel drug delivery systems. The microspheres are typical free flowing powders consist of synthetic polymer which are biodegradable in nature and having particle size less than 200 um. The microspheres are made from highly transparent glass can perform as much high quality optical micro cavities or micro resonators. The success of these microspheres is limited having provided intimate contact of the drug delivery system with the absorbing membranes. The mucoadhesive microspheres are prepared by using different polymers like HPMC k-4, Ethyl Cellulose, Eudrajit L-100, chitosan, sodium alginate, calcium chloride, guar gum and xanthun gum etc. The microspheres drug delivery system are benefited in various dosage form like nasal drug delivery system, oral drug delivery system, transdermal drug delivery system, colonic delivery, gastro-intestinal drug delivery system, ophthalmic drug delivery system, gene delivery and intra-tumoral drug delivery system. The microspheres are widely accepted to achieve parenteral and oral release. Drugs that are easily absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and have a short half-life are eliminated quickly from the blood circulation, so they require frequent dosing. These review focus on overview of different aspect of mucoadhesive microsphere, different preparation method of microsphere as well as evaluation parameter and applications of mucoadhesive microsphere.

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INTRODUCTION

The term microsphere is defined as a spherical particle with size from 1 μm -1000 μm . The microspheres are typical free flowing powder consist of synthetic polymer which are biodegradable in nature and having particle size less than 200 μm . The microspheres are made from highly transparent glass can perform as much high quality optical micro cavities or micro resonators. The success of these microspheres is limited having provided intimate contact of the drug delivery system with the absorbing membranes. The microspheres are having lead to first order diffusion phenomenon. The microspheres are one of the multiparticulate drug delivery system prepared by Emulsion solvent evaporation technique. The multiparticulate drug delivery system are mainly oral dosage form which having a multiplicity of little discrete unite having desired properties. The micro-particulates are less dependent on gastric emetine time, resulting in less inter and intra subject variability in gastrointestinal transit time. They may be cause local irritation.¹ The microsphere carrier system is made from natural polymer are attracting substantial concentration for some time for sustained drug delivery. Now a day those dosage form which can control the release rate. The microspheres are producing target drug delivery at specific time limit. Microspheres are making important part in novel drug delivery systems. The microspheres are having lead to first order diffusion phenomenon. The microspheres are widely accepted to achieve parenteral and oral release. The inconvenience of microsphere having less duration of action so for sustained release, reducing side effect and to get better patient compliance. Drugs that are easily absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and have a short half-life are eliminated quickly from the blood circulation, so they require frequent dosing. To avoid this drawback, the oral controlled release formulations have been developed in an attempt to release the drug slowly into the GIT and maintain an effective drug concentration in the serum for longer period of time.

Advantages of Microspheres^{4,5}

- (1) The microspheres are mostly use in controlled and sustained drug delivery system. Eg Ibuprofen and Potassium chloride.
- (2) It is having separation of incompatible component. Eg Buffer and Excipients.
- (3) Its having safe handling of toxic substance.
- (4) The microspheres to take a great deal not merely for prolong release but also for targeted drug delivery at specific site.
- (5) The microspheres having improved patients compliance.
- (6) The microspheres having small particle size for enhancing solubility of badly soluble drugs.
- (7) The microspheres are spread out largely in the gastro-intestinal track and to avoiding revelation of the mucosa generally to large concentration of drug.
- (8) The microspheres having high bioavailability and rapid kinetics of absorption.
- (9) It also having to protect drug substance from environments.³

Disadvantage of Microspheres^{6,7}

- (1) The natural influence of humilation products of the polymer matrix produce in reply to solar radiation, oxidation, hydrolysis, heat and biological agents.
- (2) The price of the products and processing of controlled drug release preparation which may be considerable large than those of standard formulations.
- (3) The changes in the release rate from one dose to another.
- (4) The dosage of this caring should not be chewed or crushed.

The process state like difference in temperature, solvent addition, pH and evaporation may be increase the stability of core particle to be encapsulated.

Type of microspheres

Magnetic microspheres⁸

The magnetic microspheres are supra-molecular particles that are little an adequate amount to circulate from site to site capillary exclusive of producing embolic occlusion. These having most important delivery system which restrict the drug to the disease site. The larger amount of free circulating drug can be substituted by small quantity of magnetically targeted drug. The magnetic carriers to take delivery of magnetic response to a magnetic field from incorporated materials that are use magnetic microspheres like dextran, chitson. The magnetic polymers having two different types are as follows,

Therapeutic magnetic microspheres¹⁰

The therapeutic magnetic microspheres are used to provide chemo-therapeutic agent to liver cancer. The pharmaceutical drug like peptide and protein can also be targeted during this systems.

Diagnostic parameters¹¹

The diagnostic microspheres are used for imaging liver metastases. It can also be use to differentiate bowel loop from other abdominal arrangement by forming nano size particles. Its can also be used to understand the human body work in both healthy and ill person. The diagnostic microspheres are useful in clinical information for numbers of diseases.

Bio-adhesive microspheres¹²

The application of bio-adhesive microspheres in controlled drug delivery system. Its range having very small molecules and micro-molecule, pharmaceutical drugs like protein, oligonucleotide and even DNA. The bio-adhesive microspheres play most important role in *in vitro* and *in vivo* drug delivery systems. The adhesion can be defined as sticking of drug to membrane by using sticking properties of natural water soluble polymers like xanthum gum, pectin, chitosan derivatives, dextran, carrageenan, guar gum and cellulose ether etc. These types of microspheres exhibit a prolonged resistance time at the site of administration and to produce therapeutic effects. The adhesion of drug to the mucous membrane such as nasal, ocular, rectal and buccal etc.

Radio-active microspheres¹³

The radio-active microspheres are mostly used to decrease the effect on healthy liver parenchyma and to increase the tumouricidal effects. The radio embolization method microspheres range having 10-30 nm are of increase than the diameter of the capillary. The radio-active microspheres provide numbers of radiation dose to the targeted site without injure the normal nearby cell and tissues. The radio-active microspheres differ from drug delivery system. These type of radio activity is not release from microspheres but act from inside a radio-isotope. The dissimilar types of radio-active microspheres are α , β and γ emitters. The radio-active microspheres are administered by using a healthy and better route of administration system that is simple handling.

Floating microspheres¹⁴

The floating microspheres having produce prolonged therapeutic effect at target site and reduce dosing frequency. It having reduce the chances of dose dumping. These type of microspheres are used to retaining the drug into stomach at long period of time. The drug are administered by oral drug delivery system. The floating microspheres are able to float the dosage form into a gastric fluid without affecting gastric emptying rate. The drugs are slowly release at desired rate.

Polymeric microspheres^{15,16}

The different types of polymeric microspheres are as follows,

(Natural) biodegradable polymeric microspheres

The natural polymer like guar gum, tragacanth, acacia, and starch are used as a bio-compatible bio-degradable and bio-adhesive in nature. The bio-degradable polymer having prolonged resistance time when contact with mucous membrane which having high degree of swelling characteristics with aqueous medium. The bio-degradable polymeric microspheres having rate and extend of drug release is controlled by strength of polymer. Its having a release in sustained manner. The bio-degradable polymeric microspheres having main disadvantage is in clinical use drug loading efficiency of polymers is difficult to controlled drug release. The bio-degradable polymeric microspheres are obtained from chemically obtained carbohydrate like agarose, starch, carrageen, chitosan etc and proteins like collagen, gelatin, albumin etc.

Synthetic polymeric microspheres

The synthetic polymeric microspheres are used as a drug delivery vehicles, filters and bulking agent, and mostly used in clinical treatment. The advantage is safe and bio-compatible. These type of microspheres having tend to relocation from injection site and lead to embolism, potential risk and further organ damage. These are two main types

ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION

The microspheres having used for the delivery of drug through different route. The selection of route of administration is depending on age, condition of patient, disease state and drug properties etc. The attractive properties of microspheres can be used for selection of route of administration.

Parenteral route of administration¹⁷

The parenteral route of administration is most beneficial route because the drug in solution form its directly entered in a systemic circulation and give a quickly action at targeted site. The microspheres having particle size is 0.1 μ m-100 μ m. Mostly the microspheres having used in controlled drug delivery system. The microspheres having used in parenteral delivery should be dispersible in suitable solvent. It should be sterile and free from micro-organism. The surfactant in small proportion necessary for rebuilding the hydrophobic particles in parentally used as a aqueous vehicles. The hydrophilic microspheres having possibility as a advantage of aqueous dispersibility as disagree with hydrophobic microsphere for reconstituting for parental used.

Oral route of administration¹⁸

The oral route of administration a simple way for the drug administration. The microspheres having passes through often alter the environment in gastro-intestinal tract. The oral route of administration is much important to the conscious patient because the most of the dosage form having shot duration of action. So that type of dosage having taken twice a day or thrice a day. The oral drug delivery having a easy handled not a skilled person required and any person are self medicated. The oral route at poisoning condition easily removes toxic substance. It has a less potential danger than the parenteral route. In there the oral drug delivery system having patient to patient variance in GI content, peristaltic activity and stomach emptying time. The bioavailability of drug having limited solubility in the stomach and both intestine. The absorption rate constant having increase by increasing retention time in the stomach.

Ideal properties of microspheres^{19,20}

The drug substance use for the preparation of microspheres it should having following properties,

- Water solubility
- Water dispersibility
- Longer duration of time
- Toxicity
- Relative stability
- Provide protection of drug
- Bio-resorbability
- Sterilizability

Mechanism of drug release^{21,22,23}

The microspheres having a small in shape. They having a very less time required for disintegration. Generally their having a two different mechanism such as diffusion and erosion. The release mechanism of encapsulated material provides targeted, sustain and controlled release of core material. The drug release from microspheres happens by general mechanism like polymer degradation, diffusion and erosion.

Diffusion

The drug contact with aqueous fluid in GIT, water diffuses into the interior of the particle. The drug dissolution comes and the drug solution disperse crossway the release coat to the exterior.

Erosion

A number of coating having designed to wear away slowly with time thereby releasing the drug contained within the particle. The polymer erosion having loss of polymer is accomplished by collection of monomer in the release medium. The erosion of polymer being with altered in microstructure of the carrier as the water penetrates within it most important to the plasticization of the medium.

Characterization of microspheres^{24,25}

The microspheres are characterized as different properties. The dissimilar properties include peptide entrapment and entrapment efficiency (HPLC), Laser light scattering coulter current, Photon correlation spectroscopy, particle size (microscopy), Stability and activity of the peptide in microsphere (HPLC and biological methods), sieve analysis, Yield of process, Porosity and specific surface area, Bulk and Tab density, Drug release and thermal properties(differential scanning calorimetry and thermo gravimetric analysis), Moisture content(Karl Fischer titration gravimetric and thermo gravimetric analysis), Cross sectional morphology(scanning electron microscopy, transmission electron microscopy, image analysis and scanning prob microscopy) Biodegradation rate in vitro(HPLC, GPC), Surface and bulk sterility(microbiological methods), Residual organic solvent(GC and thermo gravimetric analysis), resuspendability and Syringe ability.

The residual organic solvent in the final microencapsulated product has to be characterized. It is generally difficult to remove organic solvent completely. Repeated lyophilisation cycle under vacuum at elevated temperature may help to reduce the residual level. The temperature excess of 20⁰c may result in the agglomeration of the microsphere unless the are properly stabilized.

Methods of preparation

Solvent extraction²⁶

These method are used for the preparation of microspheres which involves removal of organic phase by using non aqueous solvent. Solvent extraction methods involve water miscible organic solvent as isopropanol. The organic phase can be removed by extraction with water. These process decreases the hardening time for the microspheres. The rate solvent removal of extraction technique depends on the temperature of water, solubility profile of polymer and ratio of emulsion volume to the water.

Single emulsion technique²⁷

The single emulsion method are use to prepared micro particulate carrier of natural polymer i.e. carbohydrate, proteins etc. The natural polymer are dispersed in aqueous medium followed by dispersion in aqueous mediums such as oil. Then cross linking of disperse globule is carried out. In the simple emulsion technique having using cross linking carriers as a carrier agents like acid chloride, formaldehyde etc. The chemical cross linkers suffer disadvantage of large contact of active ingredients to chemicals if added at time of formulation and then subjected to separation, washing and centrifugation. The nature of SLS used to stabilized the emulsion phase can very much manipulate the bio performance of the final multi-particulate products, size distribution, surface methodology and drug release.

Spray drying²⁸

The spray drying method having firstly dissolve polymer in appropriate organic solvent like dichloromethane and acetone. Then their having drug in solid form and disperse in polymeric solution by using homogenization. This dispersion is atomized in the stream of hot air. The atomization lead to the form a little droplet or to form microspheres in the size range 1-100 μm . The microspheres are spread by using cyclone separator. The main advantage of spread drying is feasibility of process under aseptic environment.

Quassi emulsion solvent diffusion²⁹

The quassi emulsion solvent diffusion technique is to prepare microspheres for the purpose of controlled release drug at target site. The micro-sponges also prepared by quassi emulsion solvent diffusion technique. These technique use two different phases for the preparation of microspheres such as external phase containing distilled water and polyvinyl alcohol and internal phase consist of polymer, drug and ethanol. In these process polymer are use to increase the plasticity. Firstly internal phase is prepared at 60°C. Then, added to external phase and carried out these process in room temperature. After the emulsification process the above mixture stirred continuously 2 Hr. Then filtered the mixture and separate the micro-sponges. Than wash the product and dried by using vacuum oven 40°C for 24 Hrs.

Phase separation coaservation technique³⁰

The phase separation coacervation method is based on to decrease solubility of polymer in organic phase and that's produce effect on the formation of polymer to increase phase is called coacervations. In these technique the drug particle are distribute in a solution of the polymer. The mismatch or incompatible polymer is added in the system to make first polymer for separation and engulf the drug molecules. Then the addition of non solvent result in the solidification of polymer. The (polylactic acid) microspheres are prepared by phase separation coacervation technique using butadiene as incompatible polymers. These technique is much important from the time when rate of achieving the coacervation determination of the distribution of polymer film, agglomeration of form particles and particle size.

Emulsion solvent evaporation method³¹

The solvent evaporation technique is carried out in liquid formulation vehicle phase. There having core materials is volatile solvent which is immiscible with coating polymer solutions. In that mixture agitation will form and disperse in liquid manufacturing vehicle phase to form better size and shape of microspheres. If the core material is dissolved in the coating polymer solution and to form matrix type micro-capsules. The core material may be water soluble or water insoluble materials. The solvent evaporation technique using volatile solvent to prepare microspheres quickly.

Double emulsion method³²

The double emulsion method or multiple emulsion methods are used for the preparation of microspheres by using vaccines, peptides and water soluble drugs. This method can be used both synthetic and natural polymers. The protein solution is distributed in lipophilic organic continuous phase. The continuous phase is generally composed of polymer solution that is finally encapsulated with the protein distributed in aqueous phase. The primary emulsion is subjected then to be sonicated before mixing to the aqueous solution such as (PVA) poly vinyl alcohol. This results in the formation of double emulsion. This is a more sophisticated technique for the preparation of microspheres.

Research Work On Formulation Of Mucoadhesive Microsphere By Using Different Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients As Follows^{33,34}

Sr. No.	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient	Bioadhesive Polymers	Application
1)	Gliclazide Hydrochloride	Eudrajit Rs 100, Ethyl Cellulose	Sustained Release
2)	Metformin Hydrochloride	Agar	Sustained Release
3)	Rizatriptan Benzoate	Abelmoschus Esculentus	Increased Nasal Retention
4)	Valsartan	Polymer Used Application Of	Increased Bioavailability
5)	Theophylline	Sodium Alginate	Extended Release
6)	Repaglinide	Eudrajit S100, Chitosan	Duration Of Drug Action Increased
7)	Nateglinide	Ethyl Cellulose	Sustained Release
8)	Famotidine	Sodium CMC, Sodium Alginate	Prolonged Drug Release
9)	Cefalexin	Sodium Alginate, Guar Gum	Increased Residence
10)	Simvastatin	HPMC K100M, Carbopol 940P,	Extended Release
11)	Glipizide	Ethyl Cellulose, Eudrajit S100	Sustained Release
12)	Promethazine Hydrochloride	Chitosan, Gelatin	Nasal Drug Delivery

EVALUATION TEST OF MICROSPHERES^{35,36}**Particle size**

The most widely used procedures to visualize microparticles are conventional light microscopy (LM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Samples of the microparticles were analyzed for particle size by optical microscope. The instrument was calibrated and found that 1 unit of eyepiece micrometer was equal to 12.5µm. Nearly about 100 microparticles sizes were calculated under 45x magnification. The microsphere size distribution was determined by the optical microscopy method using a calibrated stage micrometer (µm) and size was calculated by using equation.

$$X_g = 10^x \left[\frac{\sum (n_i \times \log X_i)}{N} \right]$$

X_g is geometric mean diameter, n_i is number of particles in range, x_i is the midpoint of range and N is the total number of particles. All the experimental units were analyzed in triplicate (n=3).

Density determination

The density of microsphere having measured by using a multi volume psychrometer. Exact weight sample in a cup is placed into the multi volume psychrometer. The helium is used to contact pressure in the chamber and allowed to expand. These expansion results are used to minimize pressure within the chamber. The two successive readings of reduced pressure at different first pressures are noted. From two pressure readings the density of the microsphere carrier is determined.

Isoelectric point

The isoelectric point is one of the evaluation techniques which is using micro electrophoresis apparatus for the measurement of electrophoretic mobility of microspheres. The different pH values ranging from 3-10 are calculated to determine the time of movement of atoms over a distance of 1mm. The micro electrophoresis apparatus having used this data to determine electrical mobility of particles.

Entrapment Efficiency

The microspheres containing drug were compressed and then disappear in distilled water with the help of ultrasonic stirrer for three hours. Then it filtered and assay by ultra violet radiation spectroscopy. The entrapment of efficiency is equal to ratio of real drug content to theoretical drug content.

$$\%DEE = \frac{\text{Actual value}}{\text{Theoretical value}} \times 100$$

Swelling index

This technique used for the characterization of microsphere were performed with swelling index technique different solution (100ml) were taken such as (distilled water, buffer solution of ph 1.2, 4.5, 7.4) were taken and microsphere (100mg) were place in a wire basket and kept on the above solution and swelling was allowed at 37⁰c and change in weight variation between initial weight of microspheres and weight due to swelling was measured by taking weight periodically and soaking with filter paper.

Angle of contact

The angle of contact is measure to determine wetting property of micro particulate carrier. They are having determined the nature of microsphere in the term of hydrophilicity and hydrophobisity. They also measure solid, liquid and air interface. The angle of contact is measure by placing a droplet in a spherical cell mounted above objective of inverted microspheres. The contact angle is measure at 200⁰c within a min. Of deposition of microspheres.

Dissolution apparatus

The standard BP and USP dissolution apparatus having use to study in vitro release profile using both basket type 28 and 29 and paddle type 25, 26 and 27 apparatus. The dissolution medium used for the study varied from 100-900ml and speed of rotation is 50-100 resolution per minute.

Stability study

The placing of microspheres in screw capped glass container and stored them at 40⁰c and 75Rh. The stability study carried out in 90 days and drug content was analyzed.

Application of microsphere in pharmaceutical industry^{37,38,39}

Transdermal drug delivery

Polymer has good film-forming properties. The drug release from the devices is affected by the membrane thickness and cross-linking of the film. Eg. Chitosan, Alginate, PLGA.

Buccal drug delivery

Polymer is an excellent polymer to be used for buccal delivery because it has muco/bioadhesive properties and can act as an absorption enhancer. Chitosan, Sodium alginate.

Nasal drug delivery

Polymer based drug delivery systems, such as microspheres, liposomes and gels have been demonstrate to have good bioadhesive characteristics and swell easily when in contact with the nasal mucosa increasing the bioavailability and residence time of the drugs to the nasal route. Eg. Starch, Dextran, Albumin, Chitosan+ Gelatin.

Gastrointestinal drug delivery

Polymer granules having internal cavities prepared by de acidification when added to acidic and neutral media are found buoyant and provided a controlled release of the drug . eg. Eudragit, Ethyl cellulose+ Carbopol BSA, Gelatin.

Oral drug delivery

The ability of microspheres containing polymer to form films permit its use in the formulation of film dosage forms, as an alternative to pharmaceutical tablets. The pH sensitivity, coupled with the reactivity of the primary amine groups, make microspheres more suitable for oral drug delivery applications. Eg. Chitosan, Gelatin.

Targeting by using microparticulate carriers

Pellets are prepared with polymer by using the extrusion/ spheronization technology. Eg. Chitosan, Microcrystalline cellulose.

Ophthalmic Drug Delivery:

Microspheres developed using polymer exhibits favorable biological behavior such as bioadhesion, permeability- enhancing properties, and interesting physico- chemical characteristics, which make it a unique material for the design of ocular drug delivery vehicles. Eg. Chitosan, Alginate, Gelatin

Intratumoral and local drug delivery

In order to deliver paclitaxel at the tumor site in therapeutically relevant concentration, polymer films are fabricated. Mixture of drug has promising potential for use in controlled delivery in the oral cavity. Eg. Gelatin, PLGA, Chitosan and PCL.

Gene delivery

Microspheres could be a useful oral gene carrier because of its adhesive and transport properties in the GI tract. Eg. Chitosan, Gelatin, viral vectors, cationic liposomes, polycation complexes.

Colonic drug delivery

Polymer has been used for the specific delivery of insulin to the colon. Eg. Chitosan.

CONCLUSION

The research on mucoadhesives, however, is still in its early stage, and further advances need to be made for the successful translation of the concept into practical application in controlled drug delivery system. Mucoadhesive drug delivery systems, are gaining popularity day by day in the global pharmaceutical industry and a burning area of further research and development. The mucoadhesive microspheres are prepared by using different polymers like HPMC k-4, Ethyl Cellulose, Eudrajit L-100, chitosan, sodium alginate, calcium chloride, guar gum and xanthun gum etc. The microspheres drug delivery system are benefited in various dosage form like nasal drug delivery system, oral drug delivery system, transdermal drug delivery system, colonic delivery, gastro-intestinal drug delivery system, ophthalmic drug delivery system, gene delivery and intra-tumoral drug delivery system. There is no doubt that mucoadhesion has moved into a new area with these new specific targeting compounds like lectins and thiomers etc with researchers and drug companies looking further into potential involvement of more smaller complex molecules, proteins and peptides, and DNA for future technological advancement in the ever-evolving drug delivery. The success of these microspheres is limited having provided intimate contact of the drug delivery system with the absorbing membranes.

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